

Physiotherapy in oncology

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Abstract

The aim of the article is to present a physiotherapeutic approach to cancer. Cancer is the second leading cause of death in Poland. The development of medicine has made us more and more able to analyze the effects of pharmacotherapy, surgery and physiotherapy on the patient, and to develop the treatment that would be most effective. Still, the number of cancer patients is constantly increasing. Both prophylaxis, treatment and all methods to assist patients in the fight against cancer are important. For many years, physiotherapy in oncology has been carried out to a small extent, or at all, which, according to scientific research, was an abnormal procedure. Physical activity in oncological patients can have a great impact on their health. It is important that acquiring knowledge about oncological patients is not only related to what kind of treatment can be offered but also what actions should be avoided so that the condition of the patient does not worsen.

Keywords: Key words: oncology, rehabilitation, oncological physiotherapy

Introduction

The number of cancer cases in Poland over the last 30 years has increased by more than 200% of the 64 820 thousand. in 1980 to 140 564 ths. in 2010 [1]. In the period of 14 months (1 January 2015 - 29 February 2016) 263 490 thousand Cards of Diagnosis and Oncology Treatment were issued [2]. Unfortunately, in spite of the alarming increase in the number of cases, the publication of comprehensive physiotherapy in oncology is still limited. Woźniewski gives precise descriptions of the burdens that should be taken into account in the individual stages of physiotherapy of oncological patients. It refers to the commonly used MET index, which is used in the classification of physical intensity and is used in the preparation of physiotherapeutic programs [3]. Not only are the methods of physiotherapist important, but you can be tempted to say - knowing when to work with a patient is not allowed - according to the principle of *primum non nocere* (Latin "first do not hurt"). Buss (2008) lists a number of contraindications that exclude oncological patients from exercise. These include diastolic blood pressure below 45 mm Hg and above 95 mm Hg, heart rate above 100 / min, temperature above 38 ° C, respiratory rate above 20 / min, infection requiring antibiotics, active bleeding, below 50 G / l. He argues that the exercises should be individually tailored to each patient individually. Bone metastasis is not an absolute contraindication, weight training should be avoided. Patients with cardiovascular disease should limit the intensity of exercise [4].

Pyszora (2008) presents the benefits of multi-directional rehabilitation program among oncological

patients. The program includes physical activity, training to strengthen your body awareness, relaxation classes and massage. As a result, the muscular strength of patients was increased and motivated to daily physical activity [5]. Pyszora et al. (2009) accurately depict the mechanism of action of kinesiology taping in the treatment of musculoskeletal pain in an 80-year-old patient located in the knee. An example of a 47-year-old urological patient with lymphatic edema of the lower limb shows an exact pattern of treatment in compression [6]. Curious yet innovative point of view is Pieniążek and Sułkowska (2016), which naturally consider the combination of "coaching" with physiotherapy. According to the author, the participation of physiotherapist in the coaching session of the patient favors his recovery and positively affects his psyche. In addition, there is a suggestion that the benefits of a physiotherapist session may have a positive effect on the patient [7].

The importance of physiotherapy in oncology

Cancer is the second leading cause of death in the world after cardiovascular disease [3]. Poland is not an exception, but even in the 40s it was 150-200 thousand. The tumors were less widespread. With the passage of time, the proportions of illnesses have reversed. In 1963, 34,500 deaths were reported, according to the Polish Oncological Association, and the number of tuberculosis patients dropped to 16,000 in the late 1980s [8]. The consequences of implemented treatment (chemotherapy, radiotherapy, immunotherapy) in cancer patients are numerous side effects (Table 1).

General disorders include decreased immunity, physical performance, decreased overall fitness and fatigue. It is also important to remember the pain that accompanies the sick in varying degrees of severity [3].

Initially it was assumed that physiotherapy is not indicated in cancer. Until recently it was thought that due to the stimulus nature of most methods can lead to relapse of the disease and even further dissemination in the body. It was widely believed that physical exercise is immunoprotective (inhibiting the production of antibodies and immune cells) and that they increase the cardiotoxicity of antineoplastic treatment. They also have an increased risk of pathological fractures. Furthermore, it was maintained that poor mental condition, fatigue, and mood depression did not favor the willingness of physically active patients to take up. As a result, all this contributed to the vicious circle. As a result of the disease, treatment was introduced, resulting in decreased performance and increased fatigue. A safer lifestyle was recommended, leading to a decrease in performance and fatigue, which led the patient to return to the starting point, the disease. The best example of a change in physiotherapy views is the ability to exercise strength (in justified cases). Regardless of the nature of the exercise, their quantity and intensity are always adjusted to the state and ability of the patients. An ap-

propriately selected physiotherapy program (physical exercise, massage, physiotherapy) improves respiratory and cardiovascular performance, decreasing fatigue while increasing physical fitness. In addition, exercise improves immune function (increase in circulating granulocytes, improve NK and monocyte function, shorten neutropenic time). Moreover, physical activity has prophylactic antitumor activity. Regular physical exercise reduces the risk of cancer by 30-50% and the risk of recurrence by 30-40% [3].

Sample physiotherapy program in oncology with a home program

The health status of individual patients in the oncological group is very diverse. These are patients undergoing remission, during chemotherapy, after radical surgery, and in the early stages of cancer. Each of them requires the proposal of another, individual rehabilitation program. In 1981, Dietz identified four main types of intervention in oncological rehabilitation (Table 2) [9].

Within each intervention model, a personalized, physiotherapy program can be run. A sample program that is part of one of the models of rehabilitation intervention in oncological diseases is presented in Table 3.

Table 1. Types of functional disorders in individual organ systems.

Location	Types of functional disorders
Locomotor system	Demineralisation, increased bone fracture risk, bone growth arrest, peri-articular fibrosis, limitation of mobility in joints, osteoarthritis, postural defects, muscle weakness
Neurological system	Abnormal feeling and coordination problems, paralysis, paralysis
Circulatory system	Coronary artery disease, ischemic heart disease, elevated risk of deep vein thrombosis, lymphoedema
Respiratory system	Damage to lung bubbles, pneumonia, interstitial fibrosis, impaired lung ventilation

Table Table 2. Types of intervention in the rehabilitation of cancer diseases by Dietz.

Type of intervention	Purpose of rehabilitation
Preventive	Reduce the consequences of treatment
Restoring	Restoration of the patient to previous physical, psychological and occupational activity
Sustaining	Adapting the patient to his / her disability
Palliative	Minimizing discomfort, ensuring maximum quality of life

Table 3. An example program that is part of one of the models of rehabilitation intervention in oncological diseases

Type of therapy	Physiotherapy			
	Physical exercises	Special methods	Massage	Other
Treatment after surgery	early verticalization, breathing exercises, active exercises, antithrombotic exercises, relaxation exercises	-	patting, vibration	inhalations, positioning position, postural drainage, learning effective cough
Treatment after chemotherapy	endurance training, resistance training, breathing exercises	-	patting*, vibration*, MLD (manual lymphatic drainage)*	learning effective cough*
Treatment after radiotherapy	stretching exercises, active exercises	PNF manual therapy techniques, poizometric muscle relaxation	patting, MLD	-

* Incorporated in the treatment program in cases of secondary lymphadenopathy, functional respiratory disorders and to prevent pulmonary complications.

Table 5: Pearson's Product Moment Correlation among HGS and each of ADL, IADL, CD4 Count and general characteristics of the participants

Clinical symptoms	Physiotherapy			
	Physical exercises	Special methods	Massage	Other
Myofascial pain	active exercises	soft tissue therapy, manual therapy, trigger points	deep tissue massage	kinesiotaping
Bone pain (bone metastases)	-	-	-	spinal orthoses, walking stick, crutches, walker, protection of locomotion (patient education)
Lymphedema	active exercises	-	MLD	bandaging, skin care
Fatigue associated with cancer	active exercises by Fulton and Else rules "often but slightly"	-	-	-
Constipation	early verticalization, breathing exercises, active exercises, passive exercises	PNF, myofascial techniques. mobilization of ribs, diaphragms	-	kinesiotaping
Dyspnoea	active exercises of the respiratory muscles	PNF	-	learning effective cough, breathing relaxation techniques, learning to breathe the correct path
Dysphagia	-	soft tissue therapy, fascial, manual	-	-
Limitations of range of motion in the joints	-	manual therapy techniques, poizometric muscle relaxation, trigger points,	mobilization of scars	postural reeducation
Paresis, sensory disturbances, cerebellar symptoms	verticalization, learning to walk, breathing exercises, antithrombotic exercises passive exercises Self-service training	Frenkel, Bobath, PNF	-	-

Physiotherapy in the treatment of cancer pain is intended to promote pharmacotherapy, not a leading method of pain relief. Musculoskeletal pain intensifies when you perform certain movements or attempt to perform them. The home program includes 3-5x physical exercise per week (depending on the well-being of the patient) carried out by the physiotherapist in the patient's home. The program includes respiratory, anticoagulant, isometric, active, passive, active, load active, coordinated and equivalent exercises [9].

Sample physiotherapy program used in oncology departments

From Monday to Friday, From 11:00 to 14:00 (physiotherapist works also at the Department of Cardiology and Internal Diseases before 11.00), rehabilitation of patients at the Department of Hematology and Internal Diseases is conducted. Patients do not have fixed hours of chemotherapy. Breakfast is served between 8:00 and 9:00 and dinner is between 12:40 (wing A) and 13:20 (wing B). As a rule, most patients are reluctant to exercise after dinner, and many refuse. They are tired and sleepy. At the same time, the patients themselves maintain that they would be happy to exercise in the morning, after breakfast. There is a constant group of patients who, no matter their well-being and their own abilities, try to cheat that they are already practicing, say simply that they will not practice because they do not give anything or because they "cannot do it". There are also patients who show extraordinary enthusiasm at the therapist's view, refuse to practice politely, but have a lot of requests for changing diapers, getting to the bathroom, exchanging dirty sheets, opening windows, closing windows, brewing coffee. It is hard for the patients to explain who the physiotherapist is and what his responsibilities are. The Radiotherapy Center is located in a separate building at the hospital. There are no physiotherapeutic procedures in the ward. There is a set of wedges and rollers of different sizes available in the ward, but no other auxiliary equipment such as balls, Thera-band, poles or sensor motor cushions. From physiotherapist depends on whether the loan will bring together the gym accessories. In patients after surgical treatment of malignant tumors, anticoagulant exercises, respiratory exercises, verticalization (first sitting on the bed, then lowering the legs, standing by the balcony, standing by the

bed, standing by his own strength), if necessary - learning to wear and wear corset after spine surgery (eg Jevett corset), learning to walk (on crutches, on the balcony, on own strength). Respiratory, antithrombotic, passive, active, active, free, coordinated, equivalent, isometric, PNF-based exercises are performed in the remaining patients, and even active free with load if there is an indication. The type, pace and number of repetitions are individually selected for each patient.

Conclusions

Over the years, the pattern of cancer has changed, and the fact that it is not a disease unit is always treated in the same way and characterized by a variety of symptoms. Attention has also been paid to a number of complications and side effects that may occur during and after treatment. At present, the oncological patient is approaching holistically, paying attention to the psychic and physical aspects. There is also a rapid oncology program that helps to diagnose some extent. Due to the fact that cancer patients from year to year is more, it is a topic that is worth looking into. Pay attention to what is most beneficial to the patient in the case of cancer, but also to the knowledge that the patient is not allowed to work (eg what type of rehabilitation should be avoided) - according to the *primum non nocere* principle (lat.).

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.